

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Residential location has been defined as the specific placement of a house which affects housing choices (Aliu & Adebayo, 2010). A home is part of a neighbourhood and should be viewed in the community setting. Each occupant has needs which must be met in the larger community. Issues such as proximity to educational, transport, religious, health care, shopping and recreational facilities as well as the general physical conditions of the environment are factors to be considered when making housing choices. A home that takes advantage of its surroundings reflects the character of the area. Location is thus an important consideration in the design and construction of a home.

Flood is one of the natural environmental hazards ravaging the landscape of mankind over the years and whenever flood occur, they result in the loss of properties, lives, destruction of farmlands etc. in most towns in the world (Ojeh & Victor-Orivoh,2014). According to Etuenovbe (2011), flood is an extreme weather event naturally caused by rising global temperature which results in heavy downpour, thermal expansion of the ocean and glacier melt, which in turn results in rise in sea level, thereby causing salt water to inundate coastal lands. It is a situation that results when land that is usually dry is covered with water from overflowing river or heavy rain, flooding occurs naturally on the flood plains which are prone to flood disaster (Omisore, 2011). Floods are the most common and widespread of all the natural hazards. The consequences of floods are vast on the physical environment, economic and social well-being of the inhabitants of an area (Strahler & Strahler, 1978; Ward & Smith, 1998). Due to sea level rise projected throughout the 21st century and beyond, coastal systems and low-lying areas will increasingly experience adverse impacts such as submergence, coastal flooding, and coastal erosion (IPCC 2014).The European Union (EU) Floods directive (2007), defines a flood as a temporary covering by water of land that is not normally covered by water. In the sense of "flowing water", the word may also be applied to the inflow of the tide. This water comes from the overflow of sea, lakes, rivers, canals, sewers or from rainwater.

Flooding, especially river flooding are among the most devastating natural disasters in the world, claiming more lives and causing more property damage than any other natural

phenomenon (Adeaga, 2008). Though not the leading cause of death in Nigeria, but it affects and displaces more people than any other natural disaster (Akani & Bilesanmi, 2011). Therefore, there is the need to understand, prevent, prepare for, and mitigate its effects by authorities concerned, especially in developing countries. Consequently, Ishaya *et al.* (2009) opined that identifying areas that are vulnerable to flooding as well as collecting and analysing information on the “elevation, slope orientation, proximity of built-up areas to drainages, network of drains, presence of buffers, extent of inundation, cultural practices as well as attitudes and perceptions” are the most effective means of ensuring safe built environment and residential dwellings.

Flooding has wreaked havoc across many other parts of Nigeria in recent years including the states of Sokoto in the northwest, Borno in the northeast, Plateau in the centre and Yobe in the north. Over the years in Lagos, flood has remained a worrisome natural problem which successive governments in the State could not effectively solve. The areas that have suffered the effects of flooding happen to be the residential estates and communities close to the coastal regions of Lagos. The present administration in Lagos State however received some commendation in the attempt at reducing some of the flooded areas in the state through the commissioning of over 120 drainages (Westo, 2010). In Lagos, it has become a normal phenomenon for floods to accompany heavy and or prolonged rains. The July 10th flood of year 2011 is perhaps an incident that Lagos dwellers would not forget in a hurry, as there were many devastating effects of the flood. On June 28th 2012, Lagos residents were enveloped by floods resulting from a heavy downpour of rain which started the night before and lasted for several hours. The most devastating flood events in Lagos were the Lagos floods of 2017, resulting in a lockdown of activities within the state and substantial loss of properties and valuables to both individuals and corporate bodies. The most affected areas were Lagos Island, Victoria Island, Ikoyi and Lekki axis. A number of houses and roads were submerged by the floods.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Over time, the impact of flooding on housing have increasingly assumed significant proportions and has become a huge threat to life and properties. It is obvious from available record that immense havoc has been sustained by individuals due to this increasingly destructive natural disaster. In a study of the flooding problems in Lagos State, Adeloye & Rustum (2011) indicated that climate change is not the culprit but anthropogenic factors. The

investigation revealed that, contrary to popular wisdom, climate change or unusually high rainfall is not the primary cause of the flooding problems in Lagos, rather, increased urbanisation, lax planning laws in relation to the erection of buildings in flood plains and the inadequacy of storm drainage facilities in the city are to blame. Specifically, the major cause of flooding in Eti-Osa is the encroachment of the flood plains by the residents especially for residential purposes (Aliu, 2015). This problem of building on flood plains therefore needs to be assessed. The Lagos state government have put many measures in place to control the rate of flooding in the state but these measures don't seem to have much effect in controlling the flood. These measures include construction of bigger drainage channels, deepening of already built drainage channels and sand filling of susceptible roads in some areas and most recently, the construction of retention ponds to accommodate flood water. However, the indiscriminate land reclamation by private enterprises, and unfriendly coastal activities all-round the state without a proper Environmental Impacts Assessment test (EIA), is another huge contribution to flooding. As grave as the flooding hazards have been over the years in Lagos Nigeria only little research has been conducted on the implications on residential choices. This important research gap will be filled by this current study. Hence, this study will seek to examine the level of flooding overtime and the effects on residential location choices of the residents in Eti-Osa.

1.3 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim

The aim of the study is to examine the residential location and susceptibility to flooding in Eti-Osa L.G.A, Lagos state.

Objectives

The objectives of the research are to:

1. Describe the socioeconomic background of residents in the study area.
2. Map the sample residential location in the study area
3. Determine and map residential location flood susceptibility index for the study area.
4. Describe the flood incidence and mitigation.

1.4 Research questions

- What are the areas susceptible to flooding in Eti-Osa, Lagos?
- What are the causes of flooding in these areas?
- What are the effects of flooding on housing locations?
- Do residents consider flood risk before choosing their locations?

1.5 STUDY AREA

Source: Field Survey, 2019

1.51 PHYSICAL ATTRIBUTES

Lagos State lies specifically on Latitude $6^{\circ}27'11''N$ and Longitude $3^{\circ}23'45''E$. It lies in the South-Western Nigeria on the Atlantic coast in the gulf of Guinea. The Island is a loose geographical term that is used to define the area of Lagos which is separated from the "mainland" by the main channel draining the lagoon into the Atlantic Ocean, which forms Lagos Harbour. The Island is mainly a collection of islands that are separated from each other

by creeks of varying sizes and are connected together by bridges. The smaller sections of some creeks have been dredged and built over. This part of Lagos is the area where most business activities and entertainment events in Lagos takes place. It also houses most of the upscale residential areas in Lagos. The Local Government areas which are considered to be in the Island include: Lagos Island, Amuwo-Odofin, Apapa (sometimes also regarded as being on the mainland) and Eti-Osa. The major upscale island neighbourhoods within these LGAs include: Ikoyi and Victoria Island. Three major bridges join the island to the mainland. They are the Carter Bridge which starts from Iddo, the Eko Bridge (formerly called the Second Mainland Bridge) and the Third Mainland Bridge, which passes through densely populated mainland suburbs to the Lagos Lagoon.

1.5.2 TOPOGRAPHY

The whole of Eti-Osa local government Area to the coast and lagoons have some geophysical characteristics quite similar to a riverine settlement. Water is one of the most significant topographical features in Lagos State. The study area is endowed with very little arable land and four identifiable soil groups. A discontinuous mineral and organic hydromorphic soils also can be found in the study Area.

1.5.3 POPULATION AND DEMOGRAPHICS

Eti-Osa Local Government Area has a population of 283,791, which represents 3.11% of the state's population. 158,858 of the total population are male while the remaining 124,933 are female (National Population Commission, 2006). Eti-Osa's people are predominantly from the Awori Yoruba subgroup, however, like most parts of Lagos State, it is currently home to a diverse mix of ethnicities from all over the country.(Wikipedia.org)

1.5.4 CLIMATE AND WEATHER

The EtiOsa local government is located within the most humid climate tropical region with a characterized high temperature, high humidity and heavy rainfall. The major factors affecting the climatic conditions of this area are the proximity to coast and the effects of heavy rainfall on the land.

1.6 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The research focuses on the relationship between housing location, flood risks, and the factors that determine how residents choose their housing location.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW & THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter addresses the literature and theoretical framework for this study. The literature covers the causes and effects of flood generally. The theoretical aspect covers the theories, concepts and models of flood as well as residential location.

2.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

Flood is an overflowing of a great body of water over land not usually submerged (Oxford English dictionary). Adeoye, Ayanlade, and Babatimehin, (2007, p.369) found in their work; *Climate Change and Menace of Floods in Nigerian cities: Socio-economic Implication* that flood is an extreme weather event naturally caused by rising global temperature which result in heavy downpour, thermal expansion of ocean and glacier melt, which in turn result in sea level, causing salt water to inundate coastal lands. They maintained that across the globe, floods have posed tremendous danger to people's lives and properties. Flood caused about one third of all deaths, one third of injuries and one third of all damage from natural disasters. Eludoyin, Akinbode, and Okuku, (2007, p.1) concluded that, the Johnson flood of May 31, 1889 in Johnson Pennsylvania, USA left about two third of Johnstown submerged under water, its rail and telegraph washed out. Adeoye et al, (2009, p.369.) found that, from 1990 to 2008, flood claimed more than 10,000 lives in the United State. In Bangladesh, between 1970 and 1991, hundreds of thousands of people were killed when the combination of tides and a tropical cyclone storm surge caused widespread flooding of the low lying delta of the Ganges and Brahmaputra rivers. Adeoye et al, (2009.p.369), argued that in Nigeria, the pattern of flood is similar with the rest of the world. Almost 90% of damages relating to natural disasters are caused directly or indirectly by flood.

Floods occur in Nigeria in three main forms; coastal flooding, river flood and urban flooding. Coastal flooding occurs in the low lying belt of mangrove and fresh water swamp along the coast. River flooding occurs in the flooding plains of the large rivers, while urban flooding occurs in towns, on flat or low lying terrain especially where little or no provision has been made for surface drainage, or where existing drainage has been blocked with municipal waste, refuse and eroded soil sediment.

Apart from the 1936 flood disaster in Nigeria, Busari et al, (2009, p.8) found that flood disaster had occurred in 1980 in Ogunpa which ravaged the city of Ibadan. Comparing Eludoyin, Akinbode, and Okuku's, (2007, p.1) views, serious flood disaster have occurred in

Ibadan in (1985, 1987, 1990). In Osogbo, it occurred in (1992, 1996, 2002). In Yobe it occurred in 2000, in Akure, flood disaster occurred in 1996, 2000, 2002, 2004, 2006. In 2001, Abia, Adamawa and Akwa-Ibom states witnessed heavy downpour and rainstorm which affected about 5,000 people. Farmlands, properties, buildings were submerged and destroyed. About 12,300 persons were displaced by torrential rain in Zamfara . Similarly, in 2005, it was the turn of Taraba state as massive flood displaced over 50,000 people (Obebi, 2013, para.3). In coastal cities of Lagos, Port Harcourt, Calabar, and Warri, there were many incidences that claimed many lives and properties worth millions of naira. In 2012, flood disaster ravaged 32 states of Nigeria. (NEMA, 2012). Aderogba, (2012, p.12) maintained that, settlements in southern parts of the country are affected most as a result of the Atlantic Ocean. Corroborating Eludoyin, et al, (2007, p.1) views, the flood events in most southern cities in Nigeria are so prominent that some inhabitants in many of these settlements have often described it as “an act of God”. They maintained that apart from Yobe’s case, which was caused by breaking down of a dam, flood event in many capital cities in Nigeria, including Akure, Lagos and Osogbo are mostly due to the poor consciousness of the inhabitants on environmental information, inadequate of spatial information on the flood prone areas, waste dump and construction of building on river channels without adequate measure for water flow.

2.1.1 CAUSES AND EFFECTS OF FLOODING

Many urban flood risk research works have different findings regarding factors responsible for flood risk, although disaster problems may sit at the interface of the natural and social environment. In essence flood risk has been conceptualized as a function of the changing climate, the socio-cultural environment and sometimes, a combination of both climate and the built environment.

Some environmental researchers argues that global warming and climate change is directly and or indirectly increasing the amount of rain and ice melting and thereby increasing the magnitude of runoff and subsequent flooding. For instance flood disasters in Zimbabwe are related to two different phenomena: localized heavy seasonal rainfall causing rivers overflowing and the cyclone induced floods leading to frequent and seasonal flood (Ghimbi, 2007). According to Karley (2009) the common causes of flooding in Ghana are intense rainfall leading to run-off, dam-burst and tidal waves, and spread flooding was a result of Cyclone Eline in 2000 over Mozambique, South Africa, Zimbabwe, Malawi, Botswana and

Namibia (Vaz, 2000). Criss (2009) asserted that the increasing frequency of flood events could not be unrelated to climatic change.

However, flood hazard and its risk could not be accounted as the only one factor responsible for flood risk; therefore more factors are needed to give adequate insight and understanding of the process.

The second perspective claimed cultural activities have significantly affects the working of the physical natural environment and that the environment is only responding to these actions. Of all land uses changes affecting hydrology of an area, urbanization is by far the most forceful bringing changes in peak flow characteristics, changes in total run off, changes in quality of water and changes in hydrological amenities (Leopold, 1968).The increasing human population in the urban areas and the encroachment and modification of the flood plains of river systems are contributing factors to the increasing damages and risk causes by the floods (Samarasinghe et al., 2010).The volume of runoff is governed primarily by infiltration characteristics and is related to land, slope, soil type and vegetation. It is thus directly related to the percentage of an areas cover by roofs, streets and other impervious surfaces at time of hydrograph rising during storms (Leopold, 1968). The increase in impervious surface such as the effect of increasing flood peaks during storm period and decreasing low flows between storms (Leopold, 1968). For example removal of vegetated land cover by replacing it with concrete surfaces in urban areas increases impermeable surfaces, thereby causing increase in overland flow and reduces infiltration, bypassing the natural storage and reducing the strength of the subsurface leading to quick runoff and flooding. Therefore urbanization increases the volume and rate of surface runoff through alteration of natural drainage system and modification of runoff to streams. The end result is a greater volume of runoff, discharging in a shorter period of time and potentially leading to dramatically increase in flood peaks (Smith, 2013). For instance empirical studies shows that climate has not been a consequential factor in the observed increasing flood damages in Africa according to a study by Baldassare et al. (2010) on flood fatalities in Africa. The actions include but not limited to poor planning of the physical environment, poor management of wastes, inadequate drains for the built up areas but also occupation of the floodplain areas. Hooijer, et al., (2004) examines that the impact of 30 years of urbanization on two sub-catchments of the Thames, showing a clear increase in flood frequency with urbanization, followed by a reduction in storage. Daniel (2012) also claimed that the general notion of heavy rainfall as been the major cause of urban flood is refuted, but lack of urban infrastructures play a major role for flood disaster in Gombe Metropolis, Nigeria.

This perspective theorized based on empirical studies that the increasing flood risk is not only cause by climate change but the increasing build-up environment affecting how the environment works as the main reason for floods. Subsequent progress in flood studies combined the two factors for flood incidence around the global,

Pielke (2000) argue that, there is a weak relationship between hydrological factor and the damaging floods, because the damaging floods occur from a combine effect of physical and societal processes, and floods result from a combination of meteorological and hydrological extremes (WMO/GWP, 2008). The flood risk is increasing not only because of climate change but also due to continued encroachment of people and properties in areas at risk of flooding resulting in an increasing potential damage (Hooijer et al., 2004). Criss (2015) concluded that flood levels rises as a result of climatic change and in-channel structures.

According to the above perspectives, flood risk can be perceived as a function of exposure, vulnerability and hazard (Wisner et al., 2004). The climatic change could be seen as the hazard and the socio-cultural context could be regarded as the exposure to hazard and the vulnerability of people in the hazard place. Therefore, in order to fully understand the concept of urban flood risks, it became necessary to examine the different kind of components encompasses the risks for efficient flood management for survival of man in his urban setting. Hence, flood risk hazard can be characterized by climatic change leading to probability and intensity of high river flows that causes inundation in an area. Exposure and vulnerability refers to the question of whether or not people or values are in range of flood waters and is the population and assets located in hazardous zone.

Therefore, flood risk can be seen as a cross-cutting combination of susceptibility, exposure and hazard and if any of these three elements increases or decreases, then the risk increases or decreases accordingly. As such understanding flood risk concept could be an efficient measure for risk reduction.

According to the description of the British Environmental Agency, the notion of flood or flooding is basically a natural event and describes the occurrence of severe rainfalls that fills rivers and streams above their normal capacity. In comparison, the Sea Grant Haznet (NOAA) webpage would refer to floods also as natural events, but they add that "... they have shaped the landscape, provided habitat for wildlife, and created rich soils. Cumulatively, floods have also been our nation's greatest disaster, disrupting lives, and often causing

significant economic losses.” Other causes for flood are elevated or high river levels, but also tidal or fluvial increase can cause water levels to rise or surge. Both agencies acknowledge in their literature that floods are a hazard, but only the Sea Grant Haznet (NOAA) characterizes it also as positive, as the creator of landscapes, wildlife and rich soils and links the economic loss of a society.

As a result, like in the case of Hurricane Katherina in which heavy rainfall caused excess waters flooding the city, low lying and close to the water settlements areas are more prone to experience floods than any other areas (Travis (2005). Grebner and Richter pointed that out in their literature that floods can also occur when rainwater or melting snow collects on the ground and cannot find a source to drain into (i.e. frozen or solid ground condition). This is a typical example where surface water run-off in sloppy areas (Grebner and Richter, 1991). Consequently, localized flooding mainly occurs when the ground cannot absorb any more water in a particular area due to human alternation, increasing risk. And Kelman seems to agree with Grebner and Richter in his article “The Autumn 2000 Floods in England and Flood Management” (2001). He discovered that vulnerability of people has increased as demographic changes have increasingly put people and property in vulnerable areas like expanding urban areas like in England in 2000. England experienced exceptional levels of rain during autumn 2000, but the resulting flood disaster was mostly caused by society (Kelman, 2001).

Though triggered by nature, floods are always somehow embedded in a social context when looking to most reports, papers or articles which are available. Floods become negative subject to certain socio-economic, political, and historical situations and constraints (IPCC, 2001b). Hence, floods are cultural and social as well as organizational, technical, communicative, and economic events (Birkmann, 2006). Despite of the risk people may face, most literature stresses the cause of impacts of floods on society depend primarily on how flood reduction is managed in the first place through governance instances. It is convenient to assume that climate change is the start of the impact process like floods, but most research emphasizes yet on externalities, triggering subsequent socio-economic change and adaptation (FLOODsite, 2009).

There is no doubt for an increasing concern on flood risk in various towns and cities around the world especially river floods that account for almost half of the deaths and one-third of all economic losses from natural hazards worldwide (UNESCO, 2008). In a span of twenty years from 1990-2010 floods are responsible for 200,000 deaths and affected 3 billion people by

making them homeless (Smith, 2013). Continuous rising of flood incidence globally and the increasing flood risk led environmental scientist consider carefully on what could be the possible factors behind this environmental problem and what are the possible measures against it.

2.1.2 Coping Strategies in Nigerian Cities

Community has different perceptions on disaster and develops different efforts to overcome the floods. The capacities to cope with the disaster impact is however different depending on social groups; poor and rich, men and women, young and old, indigenous or non- indigenous, etc. Many have struggled to relocate out of their flood-prone neighborhoods to better areas without success mostly due huge cost of rent. Being located in the flood-prone area, majority of the people are aware of the danger involved and they have tried to protect and cope with flood effects. There are many ways or of coping mechanism employed by the local people to deal with the negative impact of flood. These can be grouped as follows: economic technological/structural and social coping mechanisms. The definition of economic coping mechanism involves economic activities and diversification, including those strategies of the community linked to materials goods and resources, for instance, having more than one source of income. The technological/structural coping mechanism refers to the structural activities employed by households living the flood-prone area to cope with flood losses or damages. These include the construction of houses to prevent floods or the use of materials that can minimize the flood losses and damage. For instance people in flood prone areas such as Lagos, Ibadan and Abeokuta have taken to construct their house with reinforced material and some houses with second floor to protect their lives and properties against flood. The social/organizational coping mechanisms are those activities and or social relationship and network among the community and local government that can help people to minimize the flood losses and damage (e.g. the supply of relief materials and establishment of refugee camps house displaced people until the flood recedes). It must be noted that local people behave and develop mechanisms for coping, that if well understood can guide local authorities and communities to develop in partnership adequate measures for avoiding or decreasing people's vulnerability and expand their opportunities for managing floods (UNFCCC, 2007).

2.2 FLOODING AND RESIDENTIAL LOCATION

There are number of estimation issues involved in developing the multinomial model for residential choice. This section first discusses the spatial scale at which residential location choices are defined, and describes the process of generating choice alternatives for each household.

In the Ibadan, there is the abundant legacy of congested and poor houses which are unfit for habitation, characterized by unhealthy neighborhood conditions, indiscriminate dumping of wastes and inadequate infrastructure services (Coker et al. 2008). One of the key drivers of mortality during a natural disaster, like floods, is the structurally defective urban fabrics, and unregulated constructed houses, particularly in developing countries (EM-DAT 2015). Urban poor generally live in the most dangerous and unhealthy environment (Baker 2012). Many low-income households in cities are at risk of multiple hazards because of their spatially distributed substandard houses located on river flood plains and unstable hilltop and hazardous areas (Douglas et al. 2008). Like other African cities, Ibadan residents are exposed to natural hazards like flooding and windstorms as well as day-to-day hazards such as lack of access to essential services, quality housing and adequate environmental infrastructure (Adelekan et al. 2015). Most communities in the city lack basic amenities and good infrastructure facilities, in addition to the consequences of climate change which may compound their vulnerability to disaster risks. The proposed location choice model predicts the individual household's choice of residence to aggregated zones rather than specific dwelling units. In the context of the Dallas-Fort Worth data, the spatial scale of the aggregated zones corresponds to the transport analysis and processing (TAP) zone. There are over 900 TAP zones in the universal choice set for the chosen study region. However, by assuming an identically and independently distributed (IID) structure for the error terms across the alternatives in the universal choice set, the residential location model can be consistently estimated with only a subset of the choice alternatives (McFadden, 1978). One way of drawing a choice subset from the universal set without jeopardizing the consistency of the parameter estimates is the random sampling technique (Ben-Akiva and Lerman, 1993). The approach involves combining the chosen alternative with a subset of randomly selected non-chosen alternatives.

2.2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Understanding the distinction between the three elements that create risk; hazard, exposure and susceptibility gives the necessary information for factoring in most flood related aspects in the overall management of flood risks and at the same time contribute substantially to the development and wellbeing of the people (WMO, 2009). The models available for flood risk mitigation include the traditional structural measures (dyke, dams, reservoirs, relief channels, embankments) and integrated non-structural (land use planning, flood warning systems, evacuation, preparedness and insurance) options at the individual, institutional and government level (Correlá et al., 1998).

The first component is the hazard and the structural model targets mostly the flood hazard. The traditional structural flood risk reduction measures have been primarily on river training, construction of embankment and retention by reservoirs, aimed at reducing the flood hazard, i.e. the probability of flooding. For instance, Sultana et al. (2007) asserted that structural measures like embankments can provide protection against many types of flooding. Urban water management in most industrialized nations of Europe and America is characterized by large margins of safety involving huge infrastructure and technical facilities (Pielke, 2000). In recent time flood control measures may include flood proofing measures such raising the foundations for homesteads, keeping space for livestock in flood shelters (Sultana et. al., 2007). The measure has been on defense and control rather than on management.

Secondly, other models considered flood risk in a different angle by integrating exposure and vulnerability aspects of the flood risk. Since, it is recognized that structural flood control alone does not solve the flood risk and hazard problems, because flood control measures have been usually planned in isolation from other development. Therefore, they are reactive rather than proactive, by focusing on structural measures, and sought solutions from mono-disciplines (Shresha, 2012). Gilbert White was the first to argue that flood control measures should be integrated with non-structural methods, like land use planning to produce a more comprehensive flood management (Smith, 2013). Hence the paradigm shift from post-disaster response and relief centric approach to pre-disaster proactive preparedness and mitigation centric approach focusing on disasters as direct concern and a common understanding of the concept of vulnerability as important for developing a central notion. However, a sustainability and efficiency require a shift from the traditional structural flood defense to a more comprehensive Flood Risk Management (FRM) approach that include

prevention, protection, preparedness, response and recovery. The most efficient and sustainable reduction of flood risks could be achieved by reducing the potential damage (vulnerability) in flood-prone areas through adapted land use and spatial planning. For example more recently, a pronounced paradigm shift in this respect can be seen in Netherlands where the design of flood plains and floating houses practices became more efficient to cope with a highly unpredictable environment (Wostl, 2005). Also in 1977 a major storm that caused 20,000 deaths in the East Coast of India, but after this catastrophe, an early warning system was established when the same area was hit with the same flood magnitude, in 1996 and 2005, the number of fatalities was 1000 (UNESCO, 2008). The major aim of urban FRM is to minimize human loss and economic damages, while making use of the natural resources for the benefit and wellbeing of the people.

The third perspective argued that flood hazards tend to be better understood by the local people involves, because their proximity the waterways acts as constant reminders of the risks to which they are exposed to. Hence, their willingness to participate in the flood management planning is essential (Correla et al., 1998). Whether responses to flood hazard take a structural, non-structural or mixed measures, there remains a need for a mechanisms for public involvement in decision making for flood risk sustainability. This is because measures to mitigate flood hazard may include what can be done to reduce vulnerability and this can be done through increasing the resilience and coping capacity of communities affected by the flood.

Sustainable FRM approach integrates water resource management, land-use management, and hazard management and changes the flood mitigation and control paradigm from defensive to pro-active, from ad-hoc to integrated flood management and focuses on managing and living with floods, balancing floods for sustainable development, and approaching the decision-making process differently by learning to manage risk and live with the floods. This is because urban flood is inevitable in as much as urban development continued plus the increasing flood hazard globally.

2.2.1 THE CONCEPT OF SUSCEPTIBILITY

Susceptibility has its origin in poverty research and, generally spoken, explains why the same hazardous event has different effects on each element at risk, i.e. people and infrastructure. A variability of types of susceptibility exists: social, physical, ecological, economic, individual, and urban susceptibility amongst others (compare Adger, 2006; Luers et al., 2003). The high amount of definitions for vulnerability that can be found in literature is a corollary. The

common baseline of all approaches is that they refer to the conditions that make an individual or a system susceptible to experience harm as a consequence of an external shock. What differs is the explanation for that aforementioned susceptibility, as that depends on the type of shock, the considered scale, the reference objects and the location-specific conditions. The concept of vulnerability is non-tangible and it is a practical challenge to quantitatively capture it. A range of elementary concepts have been generated which all have a high explanatory value and represent interdependencies that are more or less universally valid.

A very prominent concept to capture the multi-dimensional character of vulnerability is the “Pressure and Release (PAR) Modell” developed by Blaikie et al. (1994) and republished by Wisner et al. (2005) that emphasizes the diversity of relevant scales for vulnerability research. Besides physical and social characteristics of an individual or household level, institutional, economic, and systemic conditions that influence vulnerability are included in the proposed concept. Encompassing two dimensions, Clark et al. (1998) define susceptibility as “people’s differential incapacity to deal with hazards, based on the position of groups and individuals within both the physical and social worlds”. During field surveys it was investigated whether or not there is a relation between the geographic location of a household, its social position and the level of coping capacities and risk knowledge of its inhabitants. Thus, the definition given by Clark et al. (1998) also coincides with the research direction followed in this study.

The definition that is found appropriate for this research is based on the previous findings: Susceptibility results from the social and physical conditions that make parts of an urban system susceptible to experience damage from a flood event (modified after Wisner et al., 2005 and Clark et al., 1998). Physical conditions comprise, for example, exposure to the hazard. People and buildings are only exposed if they do not have sufficient structural or private measures against flooding (e.g. walls, backflow flaps). In other words, a building is not exposed if it is surrounded by a solid high stone wall that keeps all water out. Social conditions refer to the characteristics of an element at risk that make it less susceptible to suffer damage from floods, i.e. knowledge about the hazard or the age of the affected people. The means by which people or organizations use available resources and abilities to face adverse consequences that could lead to a disaster are defined as coping capacities (UN/ISDR, 2004).

Pelling (2003) understands susceptibility as a concept comprising exposure (location relative to hazard, environmental surrounding), resistance (livelihood, health), and resilience (adjustments, preparation). Especially the considerations of resistance – referring also to the economic, psychological, and physical health of individuals – makes the approach very realistic, but at the same time very costly and complex as in-depth household studies are needed. While indicators referring to exposure and resilience are included in this study, indicators referring to the resistance are left out because respective data were not available, also for an appropriate evaluation they require expert knowledge that was not available in the scope of this study, and it was found during field surveys that floods with the comparably low magnitude as occurring in Santiago de Chile can predominantly be explained using physical exposure and resilience indicators.

It has to be stressed here that vulnerability is a highly dynamic component. The level of susceptibility can change rapidly, e.g. after the impact of a disastrous event or slowly with changing personal, communal or national conditions (e.g. individual ageing process, political changes, economic development). Susceptibility is to a large part dependent on the hazard: In terms of construction material, for example, this means that a certain construction material shows a higher fragility towards floods than earthquakes.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

This chapter contains information about the research methodology and techniques used in the study. It includes the population of the study, sample, research design, and sampling procedures. The chapter also includes sources of data, instrument for data collection, reliability and validity, ethical considerations fieldwork and administration of instruments as well as data analysis.

Regularly occurring flood events do have a history in Eti-Osa local government, the study area for this research. The analysis of flood events, the resulting damage and its causes are crucial prerequisites for the development of risk prevention measures. The goal of this research is to investigate the relationship between residential location, flood risk and home choices by Lagos residents a case study of Eti-Osa Local government area.

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design that was adopted for the study was a cross sectional design. The design has a function of ensuring that evidence obtained in the study, helps the researcher to answer the initial question as clearly as possible. The study used a cross section of the population to examine the level of flooding and its link with residential location in the study area.

3.2 POPULATION

The population of the study consists of the residents in Eti-Osa Local government area. The study is limited to the ten wards at Eti-Osa Local Government Area (LGA) of Lagos State where sample was drawn and generalization made to cover the entire state and country at large.

3.3 DATA TYPES AND SOURCES

The study used primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained from the field through questionnaires and observation with respondents, mainly from households.

3.4 RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

To collect data necessary for the study, questionnaire was used. Face-to-face interview was also used, reason being that I anticipate that the literacy level of the respondents will vary.

In this research both qualitative and quantitative methods will be employed to obtain data on the study. The quantitative method involved data collection on geo-spatial data and attribute data from respondent using a structured questionnaire.

The qualitative method was carried out by in-depth interview of respondent and observation. Also GPS was used to collect the coordinate in the study area and maps were created to show the terrain analysis, proximity to water body etc.

3.4.1 QUESTIONNAIRES

Structured and closed ended questionnaires were prepared to gather information from household respondents without any language barrier. The questionnaires were administered to household heads to obtain relevant data on variables affecting housing quality. These are made up of a set of structured closed-ended questions from which choices were selected from the given options. Required data were collected at specific periods on the sampled housing to facilitate meeting the respondents at their residence.

The questionnaire designed for the research had three main sections. ‘Section-A’ comprised eight items relating to socio-demographic characteristics of the residents. ‘Section-B’ had five items related to flood incidence and mitigation in the locations, ‘Section-C’ had nine to measure the flood susceptibility based on the perception of each respondent

The variables related to socio-demographic characteristics of the residents investigated were location, gender, age, education, occupation, income, household size, and dwelling type, residential status and length of stay in the residence. In relation to the flood incidence and mitigation, the variables determined by the questionnaire seeks to know if flooding is experienced in the area of the respondent, frequency of the flooding occurrences, type of flooding experience, prior awareness of the flooding incidences before moving to the area, actions taken on flood mitigation. For measures of the residents’ perception of flood susceptibility, the variables included; due to proximity to sea, due to the altitude above sea level, due to the poor construction of dwellings, due to the drainage blockades, due to the neighbourhood design, due to sand dredging, due to the lack of neighbourhood planning, due to the general climate change incidence, due to the proximity to canal or wetland.

Data on resident's perception of the measures of flooding susceptibility in the study area were obtained using a Likert-type scale ranging from '1' strongly disagree, '2' disagree; '3' agree '4' Strongly agree.

3.8 DATA ANALYSIS

Two main types of analyses were conducted. The first was descriptive statistics which generated percentages and frequencies of respondents' socio-economic characteristics and flood incidences and mitigation.

The descriptive statistics, correlation and regression as well as ANOVA was employed to analyse the results which shows variation in the significance level and effects of the various measures of flood susceptibility in the study area. The measures of flood susceptibility in the dwelling unit uses different scale of measurement through several attributes Each coded attribute was multiplied by number of respondents, which gave the variation, shows the correlations and regressions and flood susceptibility index.

In order to identify the selected communities within high risk areas and to determine their level of susceptibility, Geographic Information System was also used. A setback of 1km was used to create buffers around the water bodies using ArcGIS software. The Town planning standard setback from the Atlantic Ocean is 150 meters, from the lagoon is 75 meters and from the creek is 30 meters. Therefore, an interval of 75metres was used to divide the study area's distance from water bodies into 3 levels. The percentages of these levels were then estimated to be able to determine quantitatively the level of susceptibility of the communities. Also, topographic sheets of the study area were projected to the geographic coordinate, Minna datum, digitized and the 3D Analyst tool was used to create a model map of the altitude and distance from water bodies the area into vulnerability levels based on topography. The values obtained from the two criteria are added to obtain a vulnerability index for each of the communities on a scale of 0-10, 10 depicting areas with the highest degree of susceptibility.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter includes data preparation, data editing and interpretation. It also has descriptive statistics and also mapping of the study areas.

4.2 DEMOGRAPHIC AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC INFORMATION

This information deals with the key demographic and socio-economic data of residents at Eti-Osa local government area such as tribe, education, gender, income etc.

Table 1: Gender

	Variables	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Gender	Male	114	58.8	59.1
	Female	79	40.7	40.9
	Total	193	99.5	100.0
Missing	System	1	.5	
Total		194	100	

Source: Field Data, 2019

Table 1 shows the results of gender. The result indicated that among the respondents, there are a large number of male of 59.1% against 40.9% female.

Table 2: Marital Status of respondents

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Marital status	Single	68	35.1	35.4
	Married	97	50.0	50.5
	Divorced	13	6.7	6.8
	Widowed	14	7.2	7.3
	Total	192	99.0	100.0
Missing	System	2	1.0	
Total		194	100.0	

Source: Field Data, 2019

Table 2 showing the result on the marital status of the respondents; the result indicated that 35.4% of the respondents are single, 50.5% are married, 6.8% are Divorced and 7.3% are Widowed.

Table 3: Age distribution of respondents

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Age	21-30	41	21.1	21.1
	31-40	49	25.3	25.3
	41-50	81	41.8	41.8
	51-60	18	9.3	9.3
	61 and above	5	2.6	2.6
	Total	194	100.0	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The table 3 is showing the result on the age distribution of the respondents, the result indicates that 21.1% of the respondent are aged between 21 to 30 years, 25.3% are aged between 31 to 40 years, 41.8% are aged between 41-50 years, 9.3% are aged between 51-60 years and 2.6% are 61 years and above.

Table 4: Monthly Income of respondents

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Monthly income	10,000-50,000	54	27.8	28.4
	51,000-100,000	85	43.8	44.7
	100,000 and above	51	26.3	26.8
	Total	190	97.9	100.0
Missing	System	4	2.1	
Total		194	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 4 showing the result on the monthly income of the respondents, from the result it is observed that 28.4% of the respondents earn between 10,000 to 50,000, 44.7% earn between 51,000 to 100,000, and 26.8% earn 100,000 and above.

Table 5: Education level of respondents

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Education	Primary	7	3.6	3.6
	Secondary	51	26.3	26.3
	Tertiary	129	66.5	66.5
	No formal education	7	3.6	3.6
	Total	194	100.0	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2019

The result from table 5 shows the education level of the respondents, the result indicates that 3.6% attained the primary level of education, 26.3% acquired the secondary level of education, 66.5% of the respondents attained the tertiary level of education and 3.6% of the respondents do not have any formal education.

Table 6: Household size of respondents

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Household size	1person	7	3.6	3.6
	2-5persons	158	81.4	81.4
	6persons and more	29	14.9	14.9
	Total	194	100.0	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The result on the household size of the respondents, according to table 6 shows that 3.6% of the respondents have a household size of 1person, 81.4% of the respondents have a household size between 2 to 5persons, 14.9% have a household size of 6persons and above.

Table 7: Dwelling Type of respondents

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Dwell	Single room	27	13.9	13.9

ing type	Terrace	57	29.4	29.4
	Duplex	37	19.1	19.1
	Mini flat	73	37.6	37.6
	Total	194	100.0	100.0

Source; Field survey, 2019

With regards to the respondents' dwelling, the result according to table 7 shows that 13.9% live in a single room, 29.4% lives in a terrace, 19.1% lives in a duple and 37.6% lives in a mini flat.

Table 8: Occupation of respondents

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Occupati on	Public Servant	35	18.0	18.1
	Private sector worker	122	62.9	63.2
	Unemployed	12	6.2	6.2
	Others	24	12.4	12.4
	Total	193	99.5	100.0
Missing	System	1	.5	
Total		194	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The from table 8 shows the result on the occupation of the respondents, the result indicates that 18.2% are public servants, 63.2% are private sector workers, 6.2% are unemployed and 12.4% of the respondents are involved in other occupation.

Table 9: Residential Status of respondents

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Resident ial status	Owner	67	34.5	35.4
	Rented	122	62.9	64.6
	Total	189	97.4	100.0
Missing	System	5	2.6	
Total		194	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2019

To know the residential status of the respondents, table 9 is a result on the residential status and it indicates that 35.4% of the respondents are owners and 64.6% of them are tenants.

Table 10: Average of the Annual Rent

N	Valid	117
	Missing	77
Mean		316,102.5641
Std. Deviation		474,843.12082
Minimum		24,000.00
Maximum		2,500,000.00

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 10 shows the average of the annual rent of the respondents, the result indicates that the rent in the study area is N316,102.56k. The highest rent of the respondents is N2,500,000.00 while the lowest is N24,000.00.

4.3 MAP THE RESIDENTIAL LOCATION IN THE STUDY AREA

Fig 2. Map showing the sampled area.

Source: Field survey, 2019

Table 11; Showing the Residential location in the study area

FID	Shape *	X	Y	Description	Sample_Code
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0	Point	3.46809	6.44776	Admiralty Way	A1
1	Point	3.4604	6.44651	Admiralty Way	A2
2	Point	3.45525	6.44418	Admiralty Way	A3
3	Point	3.50814	6.43739	Agungi	A4
4	Point	3.45019	6.45963	Ajegunlerd	A5
5	Point	3.44793	6.45806	Ajegunlerd	A6
6	Point	3.44984	6.44556	Alexander rd	A7
7	Point	3.44892	6.44634	Alexander rd	A8
8	Point	3.44639	6.45537	Alexander rd	A9
9	Point	3.44788	6.45397	Alexander rd	A10
10	Point	3.44965	6.45164	Alexander rd	A11
11	Point	3.44879	6.44975	Alexander rd	A12
12	Point	3.45019	6.44804	Alexander rd	A13
13	Point	3.45091	6.42563	Atlantic Beach Estate	A14
14	Point	3.42587	6.44453	Awoloword	A15
15	Point	3.50154	6.42965	Ayo Adeleyerd	A16
16	Point	3.43048	6.46009	Bayo Kuku Str	A17
17	Point	3.43745	6.45518	Cameron rd	A18
18	Point	3.53069	6.44481	Chevron Dr	A19
19	Point	3.64712	6.4694	Crown Estate	A20
20	Point	3.65338	6.46846	Fara Park	A21
21	Point	3.63982	6.47043	Fountain Spring Estate	A22

22	Point	3.43545	6.45779	Gerald rd	A23
23	Point	3.43947	6.45469	Gerald rd	A24
24	Point	3.44305	6.45572	Gerald rd	A25
25	Point	3.43283	6.455	Glover rd	A26
26	Point	3.47855	6.4234	Goshen Estate	A27
27	Point	3.47492	6.4276	Goshen Estate	A28
28	Point	3.52277	6.43685	Igbo-Efonrd	A29
29	Point	3.42519	6.44833	Ikoyi Club	A30
30	Point	3.44802	6.44046	IruCl	A31
31	Point	3.49031	6.44804	Kusenlard	A32
32	Point	3.50764	6.42305	Lekki Beach	A33
33	Point	3.48185	6.44085	Lekki Estate	A34
34	Point	3.48195	6.45339	Lekki Estate rd	A35
35	Point	3.44213	6.44237	MagbonCl	A36
36	Point	3.48192	6.43227	Marwa Bus Stop	A37
37	Point	3.47818	6.45798	Michael Olawalerd	A38
38	Point	3.50018	6.43713	Nicon Town	A39
39	Point	3.44365	6.43986	NupeDr	A40
40	Point	3.47503	6.43593	Oba AdeyinkaOyekan	A41
41	Point	3.54421	6.44734	Oluwanisola Estate	A42
42	Point	3.52472	6.42817	Omoba Murphy	A43
43	Point	3.44901	6.4559	Onikoyi	A44

44	Point	3.45661	6.42347	Oniru Beach	A45
45	Point	3.45068	6.44299	OrokeDr	A46
46	Point	3.43454	6.44344	OyinkanAbayomi	A47
47	Point	3.58541	6.46863	Adesanya Estate	A48
48	Point	3.43229	6.46246	RasakOkoyaCl	A49
49	Point	3.40948	6.44416	Gregory	A50
50	Point	3.47614	6.4282	UpdcLekki Estate	A51
51	Point	3.55511	6.46082	Victoria Garden City	A52

4.4 DETERMINE AND MAP RESIDENTIAL LOCATION FLOOD SUSCEPTIBILITY INDEX FOR THE STUDY AREA.

Fig 3: Map showing the Terrain Analysis of the study area.

Source: Field survey, 2019

Table 12: Showing the vulnerability base on altitude above sea level

S/N	Sample _Code	Level 1 (0m-5m)	Level 2 (6m-10m)	Level 3 (11-15m)
1	A1	-	Admiralty Way	-
2	A2	-	Admiralty Way	-
3	A3	Admiralty Way	-	-
4	A4	Agungi	-	-
5	A5	-	Ajgunle rd	-
6	A6	-	Ajgunle rd	-
7	A7	-	Alexander rd	-
8	A8	-	Alexander rd	-
9	A9	-	Alexander rd	-
10	A10	-	Alexander rd	-
11	A11	-	Alexander rd	-
12	A12	-	Alexander rd	-
13	A13	-	Alexander rd	-
14	A14	Atlantic Beach	-	-

		Estate		
15	A15	-	Awoloword	-
16	A16	-	Ayo Adeleyerd	-
17	A17	-	Bayo Kuku Str	-
18	A18	-	Cameron rd	-
19	A19	Chevron Dr	-	-
20	A20	Crown Estate	-	-
21	A21	-	Fara Park	-
22	A22	Fountain Spring Estate	-	-
23	A23	-	-	Gerald rd
24	A24	-	-	Gerald rd
25	A25	-	-	Gerald rd
26	A26	-	-	Glover rd
27	A27	Goshen Estate	-	-
28	A28	Goshen Estate	-	-
29	A29	Igbo-Efonrd	-	-
30	A30	-	Ikoyi Club	-
31	A31	-	IruCl	-
32	A32	Kusenlard	-	-
33	A33	Lekki Beach	-	-
34	A34	Lekki Estate	-	-
35	A35	Lekki Estate rd	-	-
36	A36	MagbonCl	-	-
37	A37	Marwa Bus Stop	-	-
38	A38	Michael Olawalerd	-	-
39	A39	Nicon Town	-	-
40	A40	-	NupeDr	-
41	A41	-	Oba AdeyinkaOyekan	-
42	A42	Oluwanisola Estate	-	-
43	A43	Omoba Murphy	-	-

44	A44	Onikoyi	-	-
45	A45	Oniru Beach	-	-
46	A46	OrokeDr	-	-
47	A47	OyinkanAbayomi	-	-
48	A48	Adesanya Estate	-	-
49	A49	RasakOkoyaCl	-	-
50	A50	Gregory	-	-
51	A51	UpdcLekki Estate	-	-
52	A52	Victoria Garden City	-	-

The above result shows that 53.85% (more than half of the total area) of the study area has high vulnerability to flooding due to the height of elevation in those areas, 38.46% of the study area are of moderate vulnerability to flooding while 7.69% of the study area are of low vulnerability to flooding.

Fig 4: Map showing areas prone and less prone to flooding

Source: Field survey, 2019.

Table 13; Areas Prone and Less Prone to Flooding

FID	Description	Sample_Code	Status
0	Admiralty Way	A1	
1	Admiralty Way	A2	

2	Admiralty Way	A3	
3	Agungi	A4	
4	Ajgunlerd	A5	
5	Ajgunlerd	A6	
6	Alexander rd	A7	
7	Alexander rd	A8	Highly prone
8	Alexander rd	A9	
9	Alexander rd	A10	
10	Alexander rd	A11	
11	Alexander rd	A12	Highly prone
12	Alexander rd	A13	
13	Atlantic Beach Estate	A14	
14	Awoloword	A15	Highly prone
15	Ayo Adeleyerd	A16	Highly prone
16	Bayo Kuku Str	A17	Highly prone
17	Cameron rd	A18	Less Prone
18	Chevron Dr	A19	Highly prone
19	Crown Estate	A20	
20	Fara Park	A21	Highly prone
21	Fountain Spring Estate	A22	
22	Gerald rd	A23	Less Prone
23	Gerald rd	A24	Less Prone

24	Gerald rd	A25	Less Prone
25	Glover rd	A26	Less Prone
26	Goshen Estate	A27	Highly prone
27	Goshen Estate	A28	Highly prone
28	Igbo-Efonrd	A29	Highly Prone
29	Ikoyi Club	A30	Highly prone
30	Iru Cl	A31	
31	Kusenlard	A32	
32	Lekki Beach	A33	Highly Prone
33	Lekki Estate	A34	Highly prone
34	Lekki Estate rd	A35	
35	MagbonCl	A36	
36	Marwa Bus Stop	A37	
37	Michael Olawalerd	A38	Highly prone
38	Nicon Town	A39	
39	NupeDr	A40	
40	Oba AdeyinkaOyekan	A41	
41	Oluwanisola Estate	A42	Highly prone
42	Omoba Murphy	A43	
43	Onikoyi	A44	Highly prone
44	Oniru Beach	A45	
45	OrokeDr	A46	Highly prone

46	OyinkanAbayomi	A47	Highly prone
47	Adesanya Estate	A48	
48	RasakOkoyaCl	A49	
49	Gregory	A50	
50	UpdcLekki Estate	A51	Highly prone
51	Victoria Garden City	A52	

Fig 5: 1km proximity analysis (buffer)

Source: Field survey, 2019

The map above shows the effect a sample area has on another sample area within a 1km buffer zone. Each zone represented with a circle will only have effect on another zone if it intersects that zone. That is, all intersecting zones influence each other and are highly susceptible to flooding, while zones which stand alone or have fewer intersections are not susceptible and less susceptible respectively.

4.5 FLOOD SUSCEPTIBILITY INDEX

Strongly Agreed: $612 \times 4 = 2448$

Agreed: $587 \times 3 = 1761$

Disagreed: $255 \times 2 = 510$

Strongly Disagreed: $22 \times 1 = 22$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Susceptibility index: } & \frac{2448 + 1761 + 510 + 22}{6984} \\ & = \frac{4741}{6985} \end{aligned}$$

Susceptibility index = 0.68

From the calculation above shows the susceptibility index is 0.68 which means the flood susceptibility in the study area is high, taking 1.0 as maximum susceptibility score and 0.27 as minimum susceptibility.

4.6 DESCRIBE FLOOD INCIDENCE AND MITIGATION.

Questions were asked to be able to describe the occurrence of flood and the solution applied in the study area.

Table 14: Have you ever experienced flooding in your neighbourhood

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Flooding	Yes	145	74.7	75.1

experien	No	48	24.7	24.9
ce	Total	193	99.5	100.0
Missing	System	1	.5	
Total		194	100.0	

Source; Field Survey, 2019

Table 14 is the result showing whether the respondents ever experienced flooding in their neighbourhood. The result indicates that 75.1% of the respondents have experienced flooding in their neighbourhood while 24.9% of the respondents haven't experienced flooding.

Table 15: How often do you experience flooding in your neighbourhood

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Rate of flooding	Once a year	121	62.4	77.1
	Once every two years	13	6.7	8.3
	Rarely	23	11.9	14.6
	Total	157	80.9	100.0
Missing	System	37	19.1	
Total		194	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The result from table 15 indicates that 77.1% of the respondents experience flooding once in a year, 8.3% experience flooding once every two years and 14.6% of the respondents rarely experience flooding in their neighbourhood.

Table 16: What major type of flooding do you experience?

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Flooding type	Street flooding	104	53.6	67.5
	Yard flooding	37	19.1	24.0
	Home flooding	12	6.2	7.8
	Others	1	.5	.6
	Total	154	79.4	100.0
Missing	System	40	20.6	
Total		194	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 16: showing the result on the type of flooding the respondents experience in the neighbourhood, the result indicates that 67.5% of the respondents experience the street flooding, 24% experience yard flooding, 7.8% experience home flooding and 0.6% of the respondents experience other type of flooding.

Table 17: Were you aware of the flooding challenges in this area?

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Flooding awareness	Yes	73	37.6	46.5
	No	84	43.3	53.5
	Total	157	80.9	100.0
Missing	System	37	19.1	
Total		194	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 17 shows the result on whether the respondents were aware of the flooding challenges before moving to the area. The result shows that 46.5% of the respondents were not aware before moving into the area while 53.5% of the respondents were aware of the flooding challenges.

Table 18: What action if any have you taken to minimise the impact of flooding?

	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Action to minimize flooding	Drainage creation/maintenance	82	42.3	55.0
	Elevated high foundation	23	11.9	15.4
	Dike building	13	6.7	8.7
	Land treatment	20	10.3	13.4
	Other	11	5.7	7.4
	Total	149	76.8	100.0
Missing	System	45	23.2	
Total		194	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 18 shows the result on the actions carried out to minimise the impact of flooding. The result indicates that 55% of the respondents built drainage and maintained it, 15.4% minimised the flooding by laying high foundation, 8.7% dike the building, 13.4% of the

respondents minimise the flooding through land treatment and 7.4% used other measures to minimise the impact of flooding in their neighbourhood.

Table 19: SHOWING THE CORRELATION OF SUSCEPTIBILITY VARIABLES

	Duethe proximity to the sea	Duethe altitude of the location above sea level	Duethe poor construction of dwelling	Duethe drainage blockage	Duethe neighbourhood design	Duethe sand dredging	Duethe lack of neighbourhood planning	Duethe general climate change incidence	Duethe proximity to canal or wetland
Duethe proximity to the sea	1	.677**	.087	.416**	.287**	.079	.178*	.526**	.491**
		.000	.255	.000	.000	.304	.020	.000	.000
Duethe altitude of the location above sea level	.677**	1	.274**	.389**	.314**	.179*	.296**	.536**	.359**
	.000		.000	.000	.000	.019	.000	.000	.000
Duethe poor construction of dwelling	.087	.274**	1	.256**	.632**	.524**	.568**	.264**	.061
	.255	.000		.001	.000	.000	.000	.000	.424
Duethe drainage blockage	.416**	.389**	.256**	1	.357**	.365**	.266**	.509**	.361**
	.000	.000	.001		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Duethe neighbourhood design	.287**	.314**	.632**	.357**	1	.511**	.609**	.350**	.157*
	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.040
Duethe sand dredging	.079	.179*	.524**	.365**	.511**	1	.513**	.501**	.149
	.304	.019	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.052
Duethe lack of neighbourhood planning	.178*	.296**	.568**	.266**	.609**	.513**	1	.398**	.213**
	.020	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.005
Duethe general climate change incidence	.526**	.536**	.264**	.509**	.350**	.501**	.398**	1	.555**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
Duethe proximity to canal or wetland	.491**	.359**	.061	.361**	.157*	.149	.213**	.555**	1
	.000	.000	.424	.000	.040	.052	.005	.000	

Source: Field Survey, 2019 (N=170)

Significance level of .05

The result from the table above shows the relationship between the variables. The significance level between variables shows how they affect each other. From the table the result shows that the susceptibility variable has relation with other variables having a significant level of .000 to .002. Proximity to the sea relate with variables like the Altitude

above sea level, drainage blockage, Neighbourhood design, general climate change and proximity to canal or wetland are associated due to the significant level which is .000 while with variables like the poor construction, sand dredging and lack of neighbourhood planning are not so significant with a significant level of .167, .152 and 0.15 respectively.

According to the result from the table, it shows that the Altitude above sea level is associated with the entire variable with a significant level of .000 except sand dredging which has a low significant level of .009.

The poor construction of dwelling is a variable relating with other variables except the Proximity to the sea and proximity to canal or wetland which has a low significant level of .167 and .245. The drainage blockage variable has an association with all other variables with a significant level of .000 and .001.

Neighbourhood design has relation with other variables except the proximity to canal or wetland having a significant level of .031. Also from the result above it shows that sand dredging relates with poor construction of dwelling, drainage blockade, neighbourhood design, lack of neighbourhood planning, general climate change but not with proximity to sea, altitude above sea level and proximity to canal and wetland.

Lack of Neighbourhood plan from the result is related all the variables except from the proximity to the sea. General climate change is variable relating with the entire variable.

4.7 REGRESSION ANALYSIS

The table (Table 20) below shows the regression analysis of residential location and susceptibility to flooding variables. Out of the eleven predictors of flooding, poor construction of dwelling and drainage blockage are significant predictors of residential location and susceptibility to flooding Eti-Osa area of Lagos. Other variables such as proximity to the sea, altitude of the location above sea level, neighbourhood design, sand dragging, lack of neighbourhood planning, climate change and proximity to wetland are insignificant in the prediction of residential location and susceptibility to flooding.

Table 20

		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.156	.038		30.197	.000
	Duetotheprimitytothesea	-.003	.024	-.010	-.105	.916
	Duetothealtitudeofthelocationaboveasealevel	.008	.019	.035	.396	.693
	Duetothepoorconstructionofdwelling	-.074	.016	-.384	-4.569	.000
	Duetothedrainageblockage	-.074	.017	-.308	-4.273	.000
	Dueto neighbourhood design	-.010	.018	-.049	-.555	.580
	Duetosandredging	.001	.016	.006	.076	.940
	Duetolackofneighbourhoodplanning	-.012	.015	-.067	-.824	.411
	Duetogeneralclimatechangeincidence	-.027	.022	-.115	-1.220	.224
	Duetoproximitytocanalorwetland	-.004	.019	-.015	-.202	.840

Table 21

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change

1	.670 ^a	.449	.418	.12066	.449	14.463	9	160	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant),									

The table above provides the R and R2 values. The R value represents the simple correlation and is 0.670 (the "R" Column), which indicates a high degree of correlation. The R2 value (the "R Square" column) indicates how much of the total variation in the dependent variable, residential location and susceptibility to flooding can be explained by the independent variable, which are poor construction of dwelling, drainage blockage marriage, proximity to the sea, altitude of the location above sea level, neighbourhood design, sand dragging, lack of neighbourhood planning, climate change and proximity to wetland etc. In this case, 44.9% can be explained. Which means it's enough

Table 22

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.895	9	.211	14.463	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.330	160	.015		
	Total	4.225	169			
a. Dependent Variable: Susceptibility						

This table indicates that the regression model predicts the dependent variable significantly well. This indicates the statistical significance of the regression model that was run. Here, $p < 0.0005$, which is less than 0.05, and indicates that, overall, the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable (i.e. it is a good fit for the data). The Coefficients table provide us with the necessary information to predict flooding susceptibility from poor construction of dwelling, drainage blockage marriage, proximity to the sea, altitude of the location above sea level, neighbourhood design, sand dragging, lack of neighbourhood planning, climate change and proximity to wetland. Furthermore, we can use the values in the "B" column under the "Unstandardized Coefficients" column, as shown above.

4.8 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Analysis of the socio-economic and demographic attributes of respondents shows that majority of the respondents are males. It also shows that more than half of the respondents are married. Majority are aged between 48-50 years, earn between 51,000-100,000, have tertiary education, and also a household size of 2-5 persons. Also, more than half of the respondents are private sector workers and tenants with the average rent of N315,102.56k.

The susceptibility map shows that the study area has an average altitude of 0-5m above sea level making the area highly susceptible to flooding. Also, with the map analysing the susceptibility due to the proximity to water bodies, it is shown that most of the study area is prone to flooding since the area is surrounded by water bodies.

Findings deduced from the analysis of the flood incidence and mitigation shows that majority of the respondents have experienced flooding with seasonal occurrences once every year and the prominent type of flooding experienced by the respondents is street flooding. Majority of the respondents have also taken steps to reduce the impact of flooding with majority of them constructing drainages around their homes.

Factors used to measure the respondents' perception of susceptibility to flooding were also analysed and an index was deduced. Result from the index shows that majority of the respondents believe that their area is highly susceptible to flooding because of the 9 variables used to measure the susceptibility (A sample of the questionnaire is attached to this work).

Correlation and regression analysis also shows that these factors are very significant in determining susceptibility and are also interrelated in some areas.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

5.1 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

There are facts that were observed and discovered during the research concerning the susceptibility of flooding in the study area. These facts are stated as follows:

- The survey showed that the area experience flooding; often once in a year
- From the survey it was observed that the study area experiences street flooding, yard flooding, home flooding etc.
- It was observed from the survey that most of the respondents were not aware of the flooding challenge before moving into the area.
- Also it was discovered that private individuals have carried out some measures to reduce the impact of flooding in the area; the measures include; drainage creation, elevation of high foundation, dike building, land treatment etc.
- It was discovered that most of the terrain (in terms of elevation) of the study areas is between 0mm-11mm.
- It was also discovered that majority of the areas in the stud area are highly prone to flooding, some are moderate and few of them are of low vulnerability to flooding.
- The susceptibility index also showed that the area is susceptible to flooding with the index being 0.68.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the work recommends possible solutions that could accommodate immediate remedial and preventive measures to minimizing flood problems observed in the study area. Therefore, the following measures are recommended:

- There is a need for provision of standard infrastructural facilities by the government. These facilities include good surface drainage, potable water supply for consumption and other supporting facilities.
- Repair and construction of these drainages where necessary should be embarked on to further ease the flow of storm water. Also, excavation of solid waste and other deposits which are present in the existing drainage.
- There should be improvement in technology on how local building material can be subsidized so as to make structures flood resistant. Likewise, roofing materials should be improved upon to avoid building and structural collapse.
- Environmental sanitation program must be made compulsory and appropriate agency should be vested with the power to punish residents who fail to adhere to the rule of sanitation. There should be fines and penalties for people who fail to comply with the sanitation program.
- Public enlightenment programmes should be organized to educate the public on the dangers of flood disaster and its causes as a result of the habit of throwing and dumping refuse in gutters, drainage paths and river channels. There is also need for government to set up various information programmes to educate the masses on how to respond to flood disaster.
- In order to reduce the risk of flood, the government should provide adequate funding for disaster management bodies and agencies to enable them perform and execute their duties effectively and efficiently.
- Resettlement of population can be done when all flood mitigation measures do not seem to work. This measure may be expensive because alternative land and houses in some cases will have to be allocated to each household that is being resettled.

- The road network in the study area lacks drainage system to the extent that water overflow on the road during heavy rainfall. Thus, the state government along with the local government should embark on the construction of wide and deep drainage system that can withstand heavy water flow.
- Quality materials should be used for the construction of drainages and bridges.

5.3 CONCLUSION

With the trend in rapid human and urban development and the increasing flood risk in urban areas environmental researchers realized that absolute flood security is in most cases in entirely inevitable. Therefore, flood risks cannot be entirely avoided but can only be reduced to a desired level; as such flood risk management does not strive to eliminate flood risks completely in urban areas but only try to conceptualize measures to mitigate them, to an acceptable level. And this is done by integrating, structural, non-structural measures with community involvement. And finally, a systematic gradual conversion of urban land use to its natural stage could be an efficient sustainable measure for flood risk in urban areas.

The vulnerability analysis of the area carried out based on the proximity of the communities to water bodies and the terrain of the area showed that the area is vulnerable to flooding. From the survey, 53.85% of the study area has high vulnerability to flooding due to the height of elevation in those areas, 38.46% of the study area are of moderate vulnerability to flooding while 7.69% of the study area are of low vulnerability to flooding.

REFERENCES

- Adeaga, O. (2008), "Adoption of Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) Technology in Flood Disaster Management and Response; A case study of Lagos Mega City", A paper Delivered at International Symposium on GNSS.
- Adeloye, A. and Rustum, R.(2011): Flooding and Influence of Urban Planning. *Journal of Urban Design and Planning (ICE)*, 164(3), 175-187.
- Adeoye, N. O. Ayanlede, A. & Babatimehlin, N. (2009). Climate change and menace of floods in Nigerian cities: Socio-economic implication. *Advances in natural and Applied Sciences*, 3(3): 369-377.
- Aderogba, K.A. (2012). Qualitative Studies of Recent Floods and Sustainable Growth and Development of Cities and Towns in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Environmental and Management Sciences.1* (3): 1-25.
- Adger, W.N. (2006), Vulnerability. *Global Environmental Change* 16 (3), pp. 268-281.
- Adger, W.N. and Brooks, N. (2003), Does environmental change cause vulnerability to natural disasters? In: Pelling, M. (Ed.). *Natural Disasters and Development in a Globalising World*, London, Routledge, pp. 19-42.
- Aliu, I.R, Adebayo, A: Evaluating the influence of housing quality on urban residents' wellbeing: A case of Lagos Nigeria: *Int J Acad Res* 2010;2(6):400–410.
- Akanni, O. and Bilesanmi, L. (2011). Flood: Lagos residents forced to relocate ... Drowning teenager rescued" in *Vanguard: Towards a Better Life for the People*. Lagos: *Vanguard Media Limited*. (Friday, July10), p. 20.
- Baldassare G, Momtanari A, Lins H, Kontsoyiannis D, Brandimarte L, Bloscl G, (2010). Flood Fatalities in Africa: From Diagnosis to Mitigation, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 37, L22402,

- Ben-Akiva, M. and J.L. Bowman (1998) Integration of an activity-based model system and a residential location model, *Urban Studies*, 35 (7), 1131-1153.
- Blaikie, P.; Cannon, T.; Davis, I.; and Wisner, B. (1994), *At Risk: Natural Hazards, people's vulnerability, and disasters*. London, Routledge.
- Busari, A.T & Olaleye, M.O. (2009). Urban flood and Remediating strategies in Nigeria: The Ibadan Experience. *International Journal of Environmental Issues*. 6 (1 & 2): 6-16.
- Correlá FN, Forham M, Saraiva MDG, Bernarrdo F (1998). Flood Hazard Assessment and Management: Interface with the Public, *Water Resour. Manage.* 12:209-227.
- Criss RE (2009). Increased flooding of large and small watersheds of the central USA and the consequences for flood frequency predictions, In Criss RE, Kusky TM, Eds, *Finding the Balance between Floods, Flood Protection, and River Navigation*, Saint Louis University, Center for Environmental Sciences, 16-21. Retrieved December, 02, 2015 from: <http://www.ces.slu.edu>.
- Daniel DI, Juji GR, Aziukwu NA, Omiola AH (2012). Analysis of the Relationships Between of Urban Dynamics and Incidences of Urban Flood Disaster in Gombe Metropolis, Nigeria, *J. Sustain. Develop. Afr.* 14(2):520-550.
- Eludoyin, A. O., Akinbode, M. O. & Okuku, E. (2007), Combating flood crisis with Geographical information system: An example from Akure Southern Nigeria. *International symposium on new director s in urban water management*.
- Enaruvbe, G.O and Yesuf, G.U. (2012): Spatial analysis of Flooding in Delta State, Nigeria. in *Geospatial Technologies and Digital Cartography*; Proceedings of Joint Conference of Geoinformation Society of Nigeria and Nigeria Cartographic Association, November 2012; Edited by Bola Ayeni and Oluseyi Fabiyi.
- Etuonovbe, A.K. (2011). *The devastating effect of flooding in Nigeria, Hydrography and Environment*, TS06J, Epworth, Zimbabwe

Hooijer A, Klijn F, Pedroli BM, Van Os AG (2004). Towards Sustainable Flood Risk Management in the Rhine and Meuse River Basins: Synopsis of the Findings of IRMA- SPONG. *River Res. Applicat.* 20:343-357.

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, IPCC (2014) *Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability, IPCC WGII AR5 A Summary for Policymakers. WGII AR5 Phase I Report Launch 1 31 March 2014.*

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, IPCC (2007); *Climate Change 2007: The Physical Science Basis. A summary for policymakers. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Paris, February 2007.*

IPCC. 2001. *IPCC Third Assessment Report - Climate Change 2001 Synthesis Report.* IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change), Geneva, Switzerland.

Ishaya S, Ifatimehin O. O, Abaje, I. B (2009). Mapping Flood Vulnerable Areas in a Developing Urban Centre of Nigeria. *Journal of Sust. Dev. Afr* (Volume 11, No.4, 2009). ISSN: 1520-5509. Clarion University of Pennsylvania, Clarion, Pennsylvania.

NPC, (2006): *National Population Commission (2006): National Population Census (NPC) 2006, Federal Government, Printer, Lagos.*

Karley NK (2009). *Flooding and Physical Planning in Urban Areas in West Africa: Situational Analysis of Accra, Ghana, Theoretical and Empirical Research in Urban Management* 4(13):25-41.

Kelman, I (2001), *The Autumn 2000 Floods in England and Flood Management*, *Weather*, Vol. 56, No. 10: 346-8, 353-60.

Leopold LB (1968). *Hydrology for Land Planning: A Guide Book on Hydrologic Effect of Urban Land Use Geological Survey Circular 554, Washinton, US Geological Survey.* Retrieved March, 20, 2015

- McFadden, D (1978) Modeling the choice of residential location, In *Spatial Interaction Theory and Planning Models*, edited by A. Karlqvist et al. Amsterdam: North Holland Publishers.
- Obebi, F.(2013), Mitigating the impact of flood Disasters in Nigeria.
- Ojeh V.N & Victor-Orivo A.F. (2014) Natural Hazard and Crop Yield in Oleh, South-South Nigeria: Flooding in Perspective. *J Earth SciClim Change* 5: 181.
doi:10.4172/2157-7617.1000181
- Omisore E. O. (2011). Flooding , a major impediment to sustainable environment, being a paper delivered at the MCPD of Ogun state branch of Nigerian Institution of Estate Surveyors and Valuers (NIESV) at Abeokuta on 1ST December 2011.
- Pelling, M. (Ed.) (2003), Natural disasters and development in a globalizing world. New York, Routledge.
- Pielke Jr RA (2000). Flood Impacts on Society, Damaging Floods as a Framework for Assessment, in: *Floods*, edited by: Parker DJ, Routledge Hazards and Disasters Series, pp. 133–155.
- Samarasinghe SM, Nandala Hk Weliwitiya DP, Fowzi JSM, Hazarika MK, Samarakoon L (2010), Application of Remota Sensing and GIS for Flood Risk Analysis: A Case of Kalu-Ganga River, Sri Lanka. *International Archives of the Photogarmetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Science* Vol.38, Part 8 Kyoto.
- Shresha AB, Chapag PS, Thapa R (2011) Flash flood risk management: A Training of the Trainers Manual, International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development Kathmandu, Nepal. Retrieved on February, 9, 2014 from <http://reliefweb.int/report/world/flash-flood>
- Smith K (2013) *Environmental Hazards: Assessing Risk and Reducing Disaster*, (6 Ed.), New York, Roulledge.

- Strahler, N and Strahler, A (1978). *Geography and man's environment*, John Wiley and Sons, U.S.A.
- Sultana P (2007). Can England Learn Lessons from Bangladesh in Introducing Participatory Floodplain Management? *Water Resources Management*, 22(3), 357-376. Retrieved April, 13, 2015 from www.springerlink.com
- Travis J (2005) Hurricane Katrina: scientists' fears come true as hurricane floods New Orleans. *Science* 309:1656–1659
- UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) (2008) *Floods*. Retrieved on September, 30, 2014, from <http://portal.unesco.org/science/en/ev.php>
- UNISDR (2004), *Terminology: basic terms of disaster risk reduction*. UNISDR, Geneva.
- Vaz C (2000). *Coping with Floods; The Experience of Mozambique*. Retrieved September, 15, 2014 from www.thewaterpage.com/floods.
- Ward, R.C. and Smith, K. (1998). *Flooding: Physical processes and human impacts*, John Wiley and Jones Ltd, England.
- Westo, (2010) *Flood Lagos: No go area for tenants*, www.castleweekly.com Retrieved on 14th December, 2010.
- Wisner, B. (1993), *Disaster vulnerability: Scale, power and daily life*. *Geo Journal* 30 (2), pp. 127-140.
- Wisner B, Blaikie P, Cannon T, Davies I (2004). *At Risk: Natural hazards: people's Vulnerability and Disasters*, London, Routledge.
- WMO (2009). *Integrated flood management: APFM Concept Paper*, Geneva, Switzerland: World Meteorological Organization, Associated Programme on Flood Management.

Woslt CP (2005). Information, Public Empowerment and the Management of Urban Watersheds, *Environmental Modeling and Software* 20, 457-467

LAGOS STATE UNIVERSITY

DEPARTMENT OF GEOGRAPHY AND PLANNING

Survey Questionnaire

Dear Sir/Ma,

I am an undergraduate of the above named institution. This questionnaire is designed to obtain information for a research titled “residential location and susceptibility to flooding in Eti-Osa: a spatial analysis”. You are requested to kindly answer and complete the questions as they relate to you. This survey is purely for academic purposes and to guide the government policy formulation as regards flooding issues. All information gathered is strictly confidential.

Thank you for your cooperation.

SECTION A: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC ATTRIBUTES

1. LOCATION.....
2. GENDER. (a)Male [] (b) Female[]
3. Marital status: (a)Single [] (b)Married[](c) Divorced[] (d) Widowed[]
4. Age. (a) 21-30[] (b)31-40[] (c)41-50[] (d)51-60[] (e)61 and above[]
5. Monthly Income(Naira)(a) 10,000-50,000[] (b)51,000-100,000[] (c)100,000 and above[]
6. Education. (a)Primary[] (b)Secondary[] (c)tertiary[] (d) no formal education[]
7. Household size (a)1 person[] (b)2-5 persons[] (c)6 persons and more[]
8. Dwelling type. (a)Single room[] (b)terrace[] (c)duplex[] (d)Mini flat[]
9. Occupation (a)Public servant (b)Private sector worker (c)Unemployed (d)others
10. Residential status (a)owner (b)rented
11. Do you have building permit on this building? (a)Yes[] (b)No[]
12. Annual rent (please state)_____

SECTION B: FLOOD INCIDENCES AND MITIGATION

13. Have you ever experienced flooding in your neighbourhood? (a)Yes[] (b)No[]
14. How often do you experience flooding in your neighbourhood? (a)Once a year[]
(b)Once every two years[] (c)once every five years[] (d)rarely[]

15. What major type of flooding do you experience?(a)Street flooding[] (b)Yard flooding[] (c)Home flooding[] (d)Office/business flooding[] (e)others[]
16. Were you aware of the flooding challenges in this area before deciding to live in this area? (a)Yes [] (b)No[]
17. What action, if any, have you taken, during flooding incidents, to minimise the impact of flooding incidents on you and others within your community?(a)drainage creation/maintenance[] (b)Elevated high foundation[] (c)dike building[] (d)land treatment[] (e)other[]

SECTION C: MEASURES OF RESIDENTIAL FLOOD SUSCEPTIBILITY

The area is always flooded:	SA	AG	DA	SD
a. Due to the proximity to the sea				
b. Due to the altitude of the location above sea level				
c. Due to the poor construction of dwellings				
d. Due to the drainage blockades				
e. Due to the neighbourhood design				
f. Due to sand dredging				
g. Due to lack of neighbourhood planning				
h. Due to general climate change incidence				
i. Due to the proximity to canal/wetland or river valley				